

SOFTWARE DEFECT PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING APPROACH : A Contemporary review

Abubakar Sadiq Shittu ¹ and Baseerat Abdulsalami ¹

¹Affiliation not available

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Abstract

Detecting defects in software at the bleeding edge of a software development life cycle is vital. Identifying defects before the deployment of software aids in delivering high-quality products, and reduces development costs. Machine learning techniques are deployed in the earlier stages of software development to improve software performance quality and decrease software maintenance costs. This study focuses on reviewing some papers published in software defect prediction using Machine learning techniques from 2020 to the current time to determine the predominance of machine learning methodologies adoption in software defect prediction. Google Scholar was used to source research papers for this study, and data was gathered from the publications. The process involves reviewing the selected papers, writing a concise synopsis of the papers, connecting and involving them where appropriate, reviewing existing methodology, and finally summarizing the findings. The result shows recent activities and trends in defect prediction research. This investigation will aid researchers in understanding the most recent and cutting-edge trends in software defect prediction research using machine learning techniques.

SOFTWARE DEFECTS PREDICTION USING MACHINE LEARNING TECHNIQUES: A CONTEMPORARY REVIEW

¹Shittu, Abubakar S. & ²Abdulsalami, Baseerat A.

¹Department of Computer Science, Kaduna State University, Nigeria.

²Department of Mathematical and Computer Sc., Fountain University, Osogbo, Nigeria.

Email Address: sadiqshittu001@gmail.com, abdulsalami.baseerat@fuo.edu.ng

Abstract

Detecting defects in software at the bleeding edge of a software development life cycle is vital. Identifying defects before the deployment of software aids in delivering high-quality products, and reduces development costs. Machine learning techniques are deployed in the earlier stages of software development to improve software performance quality and decrease software maintenance costs. This study focuses on reviewing some papers published in software defect prediction using Machine learning techniques from 2020 to the current time to determine the predominance of machine learning methodologies adoption in software defect prediction. Google Scholar was used to source research papers for this study, and data was gathered from the publications. The process involves reviewing the selected papers, writing a concise synopsis of the papers, connecting and involving them where appropriate, reviewing existing methodology, and finally summarizing the findings. The result shows recent activities and trends in defect prediction research. This investigation will aid researchers in understanding the most recent and cutting-edge trends in software defect prediction research using machine learning techniques.

Keywords: *Software Defect prediction, Software Defect, Prediction model, Machine learning.*

1. INTRODUCTION

Software quality is one of the most critical aspects of software development., and developing high-quality software within a specified time is the goal of many software developers. Software is of good quality if the software performs all its functional requirements i.e., if it conforms to its established requirements specifications, and works under all conditions. However, an error can occur during various stages of the software development (development cycle), which may lead to defects in the quality of the software. A software defect is known to be an error or failure in software (Naik *et al.*, 2008). It is a flaw in a software deliverable that makes it behave unanticipatedly (McDonald *et al.*, 2007). Hence, error detection at the different stages of software development is very vital. With the widespread demand for Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology through Machine Learning (ML), this study aims at investigating the prevalence of ML models in predicting software defects.

Software defect prediction involves developing classifiers based on data such as code complexity and change history to anticipate code segments that may include flaws. (Jing *et al.*, 2014). Generally, defect prediction using ML refers to the process of extracting some features from software code during software development and using these features to create predictive models with various ML classifiers. With modern software's growing complexity and failure proneness, dependability has become a crucial concern, with code defects in software implementation being regarded as the leading cause of failure. (Liu *et al.*, 2011). It

has, however, been established that software defects prediction (SDP) models, notably ML algorithms, can be used to produce high-quality software. Existing literatures have proved that ML enables software engineers to predict defects in software, offering a viable alternative to the existing approach used in addressing software issues.

The ML-based models require datasets in order to detect defectiveness in software, and they have to be collected. Some datasets are publicly available in several data repositories. Among the public datasets that have been used in software prediction include PROMISE (Menzies *et al.*, 2017), NASA (D’Ambros *et al.*, 2010), and AEEEM (D’Ambros *et al.*, 2010). These datasets are also openly accessible. Private datasets may also be acquired by the individual researcher. However, most of the datasets used in SDP are public (Sohan *et al.*, 2020). These datasets may be labeled or unlabeled. The labels (a.k.a classified data) are used by the ML models to learn how to classify new unlabeled modules. The defect prediction models are trained using the labeled modules, and tested with the unlabeled modules of the dataset. The datasets may contain missing values, and may be inconsistent, as a result, they must be properly preprocessed to manage the missing values and inconsistencies amongst the data before applying ML techniques.

Different ML techniques have been explored and used in defect prediction by different researchers. They are classified into supervised, unsupervised, semi-supervised, and ensemble methods. According to Yan *et al.*, (2017), supervised learning is the most commonly used technique in defect prediction. Among them are Naïve Bayes (NB), Decision Tree (DT), Random Forest (RF), Logistic Regression (LR), Support Vector Mechanism (SVM), k-NN (Nearest Neighbor), and NN (Neural Network). Also, many performance metrics have been used to assess the performance of these prediction models. Figure 1 below depicts the processes involved in SDP.

Previous review studies have considered the early years till 2019 to conduct their investigation in software defect prediction research. However, this study is conducted by reviewing articles published from the year 2020 to date. The articles include conference and journal articles. By reviewing these articles, this study shows the prevalence of ML techniques and their extensive usage in SDP. This will enable local researchers and software engineers to understand the application and trends of ML techniques in SDP. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 discusses the review methodology, with a summary of the different existing studies reviewed. Section 3 discusses the most used performance metrics that are used to evaluate the efficiency of the algorithm models while Section 4 concludes the work.

Figure1: Software prediction Model Architecture
(Source: Assim *et al.*, 2020)

2. REVIEW METHODS

This review follows the standards for a systematic review technique for software engineering set forth by Kitchenham *et al.*, (2015). As defined by Kitchenham and Charters, (2007), a *systematic literature review* is a method for locating; evaluating; and interpreting all relevant research data to answer specific research questions. The process starts with clarifying the research question, then moves on to searching and identifying relevant papers, synthesizing findings from the primary studies selected, and finally, answering the research questions. The study question below will pique the curiosity of software engineering researchers.

RQ1: What are the recent publication trends in software defect prediction?

A. Search Process and Criteria for Selection

The selection process was based on the recency of the papers. Thus, the study chose papers published between 2020 and 2022. Google Scholar search engine was employed with various been published in various platforms such as; the key search string used was:

("Software")
AND
("fault prediction" OR "defect prediction" OR "bug prediction" OR "error prediction")
AND
("Machine learning" OR "learning")

However, to determine whether a publication or experimental result should be included, it was checked to see if it was written in the English language; if it used real data instead of simulations; and if it was available and published between 2020 and 2022. However, the re-evaluation of previously published experiments was not considered.

B. Search Results

Ronchieri *et al.*, (2020) utilized Unsupervised ML algorithms to predict defectiveness in software using unlabeled datasets. The experiment aimed to show the results obtained using CLAMI and CLAMI+, two methods independent of metric thresholds, that require no professional software skills; and are automated, addressing the drawbacks of earlier approaches employed by researchers. A set of unlabeled datasets and ML algorithms were fed into the prediction model. The values of numerous performance metrics on training datasets and predictions on test datasets make up its output. They claimed that the latter can be used to deduce information about the status of software code and, as a result, software engineers' efforts will focus just where they are needed. The results of their study revealed that Bagging, Boosted Logistic Regression, and Adaptive Boost ML approaches have the highest average accuracy across all datasets. Checking existing program documentation and datasets, such as release notes and software metrics, can be utilized to determine whether the approach was successful in identifying problematic cases.

Assim *et al.* (2020) suggested a novel SDP model for software future defect prediction. Eight ML algorithms were utilized across the Weka 3.8.3 platform to forecast software flaws. The defect forecast is based on historical data. The findings revealed that a mix of ML techniques might efficiently detect software defects. Among the other algorithms, the SMOreg algorithm, which uses vector machine classification for regression and replacement of missing values and normalizes all characteristics by default, has the best

results. In contrast, the ANN classifier has the worst results. The researchers looked over thirteen software fault prediction methods, including Ensemble, Clustering, and Classification algorithms. According to a comparison of the performances of several prediction models, ensemble techniques demonstrated consistency in high accuracy prediction, and multiple classifiers can be layered to anticipate faults.

Qiao *et al.* (2020) proposed that the first stage in using ML techniques to forecast the number of failures in software systems is to preprocess a publicly available dataset, which involves log transformation and data normalization, before undertaking data modeling to prepare the data input for the learning model. After which the modeled data will be sent into an NN-based model to forecast the number of defects. Their method was tested on two well-known datasets, and the findings showed that it is both accurate and capable of outperforming advanced techniques. However, it reduces the mean square error by more than 14% on average while increasing the squared correlation coefficient by more than 8%.

Chen *et al.* (2020) developed a system for immediately obtaining program prediction results without feature extraction tools. This was done to bridge the gap between deep learning and defect prediction. The system was accomplished by envisioning software as images, extracting image characteristics using the self-attention technique, transferring sample distributions between projects, and finally loading the image files into the feed for fault prediction. They developed a mapping to transform the files into images because the input data for the network model based on the Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) structure should be in the form of images. After visualizing the result, the experimental findings on ten open-source projects suggested that deep learning can be used effectively for defect detection.

In another study by Hasanpour *et al.* (2020), they proposed that the Stack Sparse Auto-Encoder (SSAE) and Deep Belief Network (DBN) can be used to categorize National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA) datasets that are unbalanced and have insufficient samples. According to their findings, these models are more accurate than other approaches. Although the findings achieved for specific datasets are outstanding, others, which lack adequate samples and suffer from data unbalancing, produced unsatisfactory results. Meanwhile, SSAE has the best generalization ability in the numerical model.

Jin (2021) used a distance metric learning method based on cost-sensitive learning (CSL) to implement software defect prediction. In his study, the impact of sample class imbalance was reduced, and it was applied to the Large Margin Distribution Machine (LDM) to replace the typical kernel function. He investigated how to improve and optimize LDM using CSL and then used the improved LDM as the SDP model, dubbed CS-ILDM. The proposed CS-ILDM is applied to five data sets from the repository. The result shows good model performance, and also indicated that the model can lower the cost of misprediction and prevent the impact of sample class imbalance.

Seven ML's performance on healthcare datasets was measured using Relative Absolute Error (RAE), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), Root Relative Squared Error (RRSE), Recall, F-measure, and Accuracy by Khan (2021). The ML techniques include Multilayer Perceptron (MLP), SVM, DT, Radial Basis Function (RBF), RF, Hidden Markov Model (HMM), Credal Decision Tree (CDT), k-NN, average one dependency estimator, and NB. The best performance is reached by RF., which has an average accuracy of 88.32 % and a rank value of 2.96, while SVM has an average accuracy of 87.99 % and a rank value of 3.83. CDT, which is ranked third, has an average accuracy of 87.88 % and a rank value of 3.62.

Zhang *et al.* (2021) compared and analyzed the effects of three ML-based software defect prediction models, namely LR, SVM, and Back Propagation Neural Network (BPNN) model. The BPNN predicted their effects while comparing and analyzing the experimental

results. Precision, Recall, and F-measure was used to obtain meaningful experimental data. When the precision, Recall, and F-Measure values of the data are combined, the prediction accuracy of the SVM model is high, but finding the optimum parameters to use in the model was challenging, and the prediction ability is unstable.

Shi *et al.*, (2021) proposed a new framework to represent source code called multi-perspective tree embedding (MPT embedding), an unsupervised learning method. They extracted nodes in abstract syntax trees (ASTs) from three perspectives, and each perspective has a different representation of the same node. Then comes the essential information about nodes from these various forms. To make these multiple viewpoints of information more universal and expressive for varied software projects, they utilized sub-token splitting, in addition to the structural information which is unsupervised and encoded as distinct embedding vectors based on separate co-occurrence windows, where each vector maps to a particular sub-token in the node. Then, serialization is used to organize the nodes into a linear series, and the AST is encoded as an embedding sequence. The defect classifier could learn the defect-prone codes more precisely and recognize defective samples more effectively. Compared to existing source code-based approaches, the MPT-Embedding representation learning method depicts code from three perspectives and embeds its structural information, giving it additional options.

Rahim *et al.*, (2021) developed a framework to predict software defects. The framework was separated into three primary processes, the first of which is data preprocessing, which includes noise removal and normalization. Following that, essential features are identified, feature extraction is performed using correlation-based analysis, and ML models such as NB and linear regression are applied. According to the results, the proposed method achieved 98.7% accuracy with NB.

Lin and Lu, (2021) proposed a new SDP approach for generating semantic features in the Abstract Syntax Tree (AST) that took both semantic and structural information into account by combining generated semantic features with handcrafted software metrics to form standard features, leveraging nonlinear features and statistical characteristics. On eight open-source projects from the PROMISE repository, the approach outperformed referential methods in the experiments. They claimed that only a token sequence can identify the tree structure of an AST; as a result, they developed a framework called Semantic Feature Learning via Dual Sequences (FLDS), which can capture both semantic and structural information in an AST for feature development. The method automatically employs a neural network based on bi-directional long short-term memory (BiLSTM) to create semantic characteristics from dual sequences for SDP automatically. The methodology outperforms many state-of-the-art baseline SDP methods in an empirical analysis of eight open-source Java programs from the PROMISE repository.

3. PERFORMANCE METRICS

The different parameters that are commonly used for measuring the efficiency of the ML models includes:

Classification Accuracy: This metric measures a classification model's performance by dividing the number of correct predictions by the total number of predictions. It is the most commonly used statistic for evaluating classifier models since it is simple to calculate and understand.

$$(1.1)$$

Precision: It is the measure of the degree to which repeated predictions under unchanged conditions show the same results. It is determined by dividing the number of correct positive defects by the number of positively predicted defects by the classifier. A precision value close to 1 is good.

(1.2)

Recall: It is the measure of the degree of the correctness of the algorithm while classifying a particular class. It is the number of correct positive defects divided by the number of all relevant samples.

(1.3)

F1 Score: Also known as F-measure. It is the measure of a test's accuracy. It is calculated as the harmonic mean of precision and recall, and it has a range of [0, 1].

(1.4)

Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC): The performance of a binary classifier is also depicted by the ROC curve. The graphical representation of the ROC curve is the plot between true positive rate (TPR) and false-positive rate (FPR) at various threshold values.

Also, Statistical metrics are employed in determining the efficiency of the ML models. Among the most commonly used ones are Correlation coefficient (R^2), Mean Absolute Error (MAE), Relative Absolute Error (RAE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and Root Relative Squared Error (RRSE). These metrics measure the error rate between the number of actual defects in the datasets, and the number of predicted defects by the ML algorithm.

4. CONCLUSION

With the rapid development of more sophisticated and complex software systems comes the need for quick and accurate methods for detecting potential defects in the source code of the software, and with the widespread demand for Artificial Intelligence (AI) technology through Machine Learning, there is a need for software engineers to leverage ML techniques towards producing high-quality software. This study conducts a review investigation of recent fundamental activities in SDP research using ML techniques, and the result shows recent activities and trends in defect prediction research. It is hoped that this investigation will help researchers to get an idea about the recent activities of the SDP research.

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